

MINDFULNESS, PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL, AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING STRATEGIES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Mindfulness, Psychological Capital, and English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students

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Abstract

Poor English language learning strategies are a problem in education. This study aimed to determine the significance of the combined degree of influence of mindfulness and psychological capital on English language learning strategies of senior high school students. Using a multiple linear regression design involving 160 samples selected students through convenient sampling, the researcher found that the predictive variables had a significant combined degree of influence, on the criterion variable. Thus, the social cognitive theory on self-regulation was affirmed. Implementation of mindfulness practices, integration of self-regulation training, provision of feedback and support, continuous evaluation and adaptation of self-regulation interventions, and production of research that further validates the theory was recommended.

Keywords: *mindfulness, psychological capital, english language learning strategies, senior high school students*

Introduction

English is an indispensable cornerstone in our interconnected global landscape, functioning as the universal communication medium spanning academia, commerce, and technological innovation. English holds immense importance for Senior High School students, serving as a skill and a key means to academic accomplishments, career prospects, and meaningful cross-cultural connections (Liu and Han, 2022). However, this journey is laden with notable difficulties, particularly strategies for learning the English language, and it plays a crucial part in education.

Wahyudin and Rido (2020) pointed out that students exhibit diverse learning strategies. This suggests that there should be a consistent process in the language learning processes. This unsettling idea was further highlighted by Mandasari and Oktaviani (2018), who pointed out the variety of English language learning strategies used by the students. These difficulties pose a serious problem in reaching educational objectives, highlighting the need for a thorough understanding of the changes at play.

Additional concern has been observed by Fortes et al. (2023), who pointed out that students in the Philippines fail to acknowledge and value the distinctive learning strategies that the students employ. This problem points to a widespread mismatch between students' learning strategies and their English language learning, which is a major hindrance to both academic success and effective language learning. Ella (2018) also stated that students' choice of learning strategies is a strong indicator of their performance in L2. This predictive factor may miss other important factors, resulting in incorrect expectations and strategies for language instruction. This makes it harder for students to anchor their strategies to learning English to better suit their cognitive abilities, which results in less ideal and lower academic achievement. This leads to students becoming academically less confident.

At the National High School, wherein the researcher is currently affiliated, few of the students demonstrated a disinterest in class activities or spending their leisure time in academic endeavors. They found it difficult to record new words they heard or to at least communicate with friends or peers in English. As the educational landscape changed, the integration of English language learning strategies became a crucial factor in determining learners' access to academic, economic, and social opportunities outside of their surrounding communities (Zein et al., 2020).

This study aimed to investigate the potentially significant impact of mindfulness practices—such as description, observation, acting with awareness, non-judgment, and non-reactivity—as well as psychological capital, which includes optimism, resilience, self-efficacy, and hope, on senior high school students' English language learning strategies. The researcher saw the pressing necessity of delving deeper into the interconnected dynamics of these factors. Teachers and policymakers can develop evidence-based interventions to better serve Senior High School students' specific needs and increase the efficacy of their English language learning strategies.

Research Questions

This study aimed to ascertain the relationship between mindfulness and psychological capital, as well as how these factors affect the English language learning strategies of senior high school students. It specifically aimed to investigate the following inquiries:

1. What is the level of mindfulness of senior high school students in terms of:
 - 1.1. observation;
 - 1.2. description;
 - 1.3. acting with awareness;
 - 1.4. non-judgment; and
 - 1.5. non-reactivity?

2. What is the level of psychological capital of senior high school students in terms of:
 - 2.1. optimism;
 - 2.2. resilience;
 - 2.3. self-efficacy; and
 - 2.4. hope?
3. What is the level of English language learning strategies of senior high school students in terms of:
 - 3.1. speaking;
 - 3.2. listening;
 - 3.3. reading; and
 - 3.4. writing?
4. Is there a significant relationship between mindfulness and English language learning strategies for senior high school students?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the psychological capital and English language learning strategies for senior high school students?
6. Is there an indicator of mindfulness that significantly influences senior high school students' English language learning strategies?
7. Is there an indicator of psychological capital that significantly influences senior high school students' English language learning strategies?
8. Is there a combined significant influence of mindfulness and psychological capital on the English language learning strategies of senior high school students?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive correlation-based quantitative research design. With this non-experimental technique, the researcher explored the link between three variables in a real-world situation without employing manipulation or control. In correlational investigations, the researcher evaluated the degree of variation between variables based on their closeness. Yun et al. (2014) stated this approach establishes the presence and extent to which three variables change simultaneously. This study aimed to ascertain whether mindfulness and psychological capital influence senior high school students' English language learning strategies, and the descriptive-correlational approach was deemed the most suitable choice.

Respondents

This study utilizes convenient sampling due to the respondents' availability and ease of access. Every subject was chosen randomly from the rest of the population in a single phase (Sharma, 2017). Convenient sampling was found to be the most suitable method for the study, given the limitations of time, resources, and access to the target population when choosing a respondent. Through this technique, the researcher was able to immediately get a study respondents. The researcher selected 160 respondents from three specific senior high schools. The data then obtained and were statistically computed.

Instrument

In order to measure the levels of mindfulness variable, the researcher adapted the Five Facet Mindfulness Questionnaire (FFMQ-15) developed by Baer et al. (2022). The students were asked to rate using the following scale: 5 - strongly agree, 4 - agree, 3 - neutral, 2 - disagree, 1 - strongly disagree, and N/A - not applicable.

To measure the levels of psychological capital, the researcher adapted the Psychological Capital Questionnaire (PCQ) from Luthans et al. (2007). The students were asked to rate using the following scale: 5 - strongly agree, 4 - agree, 3 - neutral, 2 - disagree, 1 - strongly disagree, and N/A - not applicable.

To assess the levels of English language learning strategies of senior high school students, the researcher adapted the Language Learning Strategy Questionnaire (LLSQ) created by Setiyadi (2016). The students were asked to rate their level of English language learning strategies using the following scale: 5 for strongly agree, 4 for agree, 3 for neutral, 2 for disagree, 1 for strongly disagree, and N/A for items not applicable. This allowed researchers to determine the extent of English language learning strategies among Senior High School students.

Lastly, there were fifty-five components in the research instrument. For the first independent variable, there were fifteen items in Part 1, twenty items for the second independent variable, and twenty more items for the dependent variable in Part 3. This questionnaire underwent a pilot test to assess its reliability after being validated by a panel of experts.

Procedure

To gather the data for the study, the researcher underwent the subsequent procedures:

Asking for Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher obtained ethical clearance from the HCDC-REC following the proposal defense. Once authorized, the researcher sought approval from the Graduate School and the Office of the Vice President for Academic Affairs, with the adviser's endorsement, to conduct the study on Senior High School students' mindfulness, psychological capital, and English language learning strategies. The researcher then sent a letter and sought authorization in writing to carry out the study from the Graduate School Dean, the Division Office of Davao City, the office of the cluster supervisor, and the principals of the three schools. Upon approval, the researcher proceeded to the study location as recommended.

Administration and Retrieval of Questionnaires. Before disseminating the survey instrument, the researcher distributed the Informed Consent and Assent Forms to the parents and respondents and allowed them to ask questions related to the research. In school A, the parents or legal guardians of the respondents were given the informed consent forms face-to-face. The parents and respondents were asked to sign the Informed Consent and Assent Form after it was made explicit and confirmed that they had no questions. In schools B and C, the researcher handed the consent forms to the respondents for parents' approval and then obtained permission from the respondents whose parents had consented. The researcher then handed the survey forms to the respondents. The forms above were retrieved once completed. The researcher correctly explained to the respondents how to complete the provided questionnaires. During the actual survey administration, the researcher translated each indicator question into the respondents' native tongue to ensure they understood it and gave a suitable response. One hundred sixty senior high school students answered the instrument in three different schools. The researcher collected all completed questionnaires once the respondents had answered the questions honestly and supplied all required data. Respondents were not reprimanded or forced to continue if they so chose. They were still qualified to receive the study's benefits.

Gathering and Tabulation of Data. After the survey's effective distribution and retrieval, the information was collated and computed. Then, the proper statistical instruments were used to obtain the information required for additional interpretation and analysis. The next steps included establishing findings, implications, conclusions, and recommendations. Finally, the researcher will seek permission to publish from the Holy Cross of Davao College's Research Ethics Committee.

Data Analysis

The researcher utilized the following statistical tools to analyze the study's findings:

Mean: This was employed to describe Senior High School students' level of mindfulness, psychological capital, and English language learning strategies addressing the first three objectives.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient: To fulfill the fourth, fifth, and eighth objectives, this statistical technique was utilized to evaluate the relevance of the relationship between mindfulness, psychological capital, and English language learning strategies of Senior High School students.

Regression Analysis: This method was employed to determine which mindfulness and psychological capital indicators substantially impacted Senior High School students' English language learning strategies.

Ethical Considerations

In order to protect the rights, welfare, and dignity of research respondents, ethical consideration is essential. Prioritizing the safety of study respondents and making sure they are treated fairly, respectfully, and in confidence at all times should be the first priority of the researcher. In the scientific community, ethical research procedures foster credibility, trust, and integrity while ethically and respectfully expanding knowledge. It is widely accepted that upholding the nine ethical consideration criteria is essential to safeguarding research subjects' rights. DOST mandated it, PHREB upheld it, and HCDC followed suit. In order to protect the welfare, rights, and security of study respondents, the researcher complied with regulatory criteria as stipulated by the DOST Administrative Order 2007-001 and the Philippine Health Study Ethics Board (PHREB, 2017). Furthermore, the researcher fulfilled the conditions set forth by the Holy Cross of Davao College Research Ethics Committee. The following nine ethical criteria were among the goals of PHREB and HCDC-REC that the researcher adhered to: social value; informed consent and assent; risk, benefit, and safety; privacy and data confidentiality; justice; transparency; qualifications of researchers; adequacy of facilities; and community involvement.

Social Value. This paper helped determine higher education teachers' attitudes, self-efficacy, competencies, and research culture. The study's findings are relevant to the Department of Education (DepEd) because they can help plan and enhance the curriculum. To make education more current and relevant, school administrators might use the findings to incorporate scientific literacy and topics related to mindfulness and psychological capital into their curricula. Moreover, this study offers Senior High School students access to an enriched curriculum to enhance their awareness of the significance of personal responsibility, ethical language usage, and the cultivation of self-worth and dignity through values such as honesty, fairness, personal integrity, and respect for oneself and others. It also enhances students' language learning strategies, promoting practical English skills. With this understanding, English language learning strategies may become more attractive and pertinent to students.

Informed Consent and Assent. Informed consent and assent forms were required to protect the rights of the respondents as self-governing individuals and to ensure the voluntary participation of the respondents, ensuring they were not coerced and could withdraw anytime for any reason. In order to build trust and openness between the researcher, the parents, and the respondents, informed consent

and assent were completed before responding to the survey. In school A, the parents and legal guardians of the respondents were given the informed consent forms face-to-face. This was distributed during the third quarter of the general parents and teachers conference. The researcher communicated the contents of the informed consent forms to parents using the local language, signifying that the researcher explained the form in vernacular. The researcher ensured that section II of the informed consent was presented in vernacular to facilitate clear comprehension by the parents. The parents then affixed their signatures to signify their approval of their children's participation in the study. In schools B and C, the researcher handed the consent forms to the respondents for parents' approval and then obtained permission from the respondents whose parents had consented. Only those students whose parents had consented and affixed their signatures were given the assent forms for their approval to be part of the study's respondent. Also, only the respondents who filled out the informed assent had given the survey questionnaire where they've answered during their common free time separately by school

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The researcher acknowledged the risk, precisely the possibility of holding over the students during the data-gathering procedure and parents during the parent and teacher conference. To address this, the researcher provided simple snacks to alleviate hunger and keep the students and parents engaged while completing the forms. The researcher also prioritized the research respondents' rights, safety, and well-being. The study was conducted during the respondents' free time, and no classes were disrupted. The respondents undoubtedly benefited from the findings and recommendations of this study through the improved instructional approach of teachers in their various English language learning classes. In addition, the students could avail themselves of the enhanced curriculum to boost their English language strategies for better learning.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The respondents' anonymity and confidentiality were maintained by not revealing their names or identities when collecting data, analyzing it, or presenting the study findings. The respondents' confidentiality and privacy were carefully maintained during data collection, processing, and distribution. The answers derived from the respondents were kept strictly confidential. The respondents' names were anonymous; only the researcher could check and handle the students' responses. In compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the collected data and the identity of the research respondents remained confidential. The researcher upheld the rights of the respondents to be protected from all forms of information, whether private, personal, or sensitive. She placed the hard copies of the data in a folder and stored them in her closet, where the researcher had the only key. She created a secure password for the soft copies on her hard drive. She intends to shred the hard copies of the data and delete the soft copy once the study concludes.

Justice. Respondents were selected through a convenient sampling technique in this study, where the research respondents were based on their easy accessibility and availability and were willing to take part in the research study. Furthermore, the researcher ensured that the respondents felt comfortable throughout the study. Snacks and educational tokens (ball-point pens) were provided to the respondents as a form of gratitude for their participation. The respondents were also duly acknowledged for their significant participation in the completion of the study by recognizing their involvement in the acknowledgment section of the manuscript.

Transparency. The researcher made sure that there was no conflict arises. The researcher maintained professionalism, respected reciprocity, and notified the appropriate parties, particularly the panel members, research adviser, research ethics committee, and most importantly, the study's respondents about the study's findings. The researcher will also distribute a copy of the manuscript to the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), the Department of Education (DepEd), the Graduate School, and the school where the research was conducted. The respondents will also receive an e-mailed digital copy of the research study from the researcher. She is willing to present the findings to any local or global research congress to make new knowledge more widely available if given the opportunity.

Qualification of Researcher. The researcher held a teaching license and possessed a Bachelor's degree in Secondary Education with a major in English. She enrolled in a private higher education institution to pursue a Master's degree in English Language Teaching with a thesis proposal writing and defense course called "Thesis A and B." She also underwent research-related training, including the Graduate School Research Workshop for Publication on September 24, 2022. Additionally, the researcher had conducted research, participated in paneling, accepted advisees, analyzed data, and joined fora. With her background, she felt knowledgeable and competent in the field, equipped to study Senior High School students' mindfulness, psychological capital, and English language learning strategies. She also ensured to seek assistance from experts, especially her research adviser and teacher.

Adequacy of Facilities. The sufficiency of the available facilities indicated the appropriateness of the respondents' exposure and knowledge. The classroom requirement for data collection like space, ventilation, and cleanliness were checked to ensure that the researcher's workspaces met the necessary standards for equity, safety, interdepartmental collaboration, asset protection, and workflow efficiency. The researcher sincerely inquired about the most convenient time for the respondents to complete the survey questionnaires. As it was in-person, the researcher collected the information in a spacious, clean, and well-ventilated classroom.

Community Involvement. The researcher made sure that the crafted survey items did not contain any form of bias or discrimination against people from any background or circumstance. The researcher made sure that neither the questionnaire nor the data collection process did not include any discrimination against any group on the basis of ethnicity, gender, religion, and/or culture. In addition, the researcher handled the respondents with respect and ensured that the survey's questions and choices were impartial and did not single out any individual based on their gender, educational attainment, or cultural heritage. Throughout the study, the researcher worked hard

to maintain the respondents' dignity and respect in accordance with local traditions and cultural norms.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the study's findings, which resulted from the data analysis. The goal of this section is to answer the research questions posed in the previous section.

Level of Mindfulness of Senior High School Students

Table 1 shows the level of mindfulness among Senior High School students, along with its indicators: description, observation, acting with awareness, non-judgment, and non-reactivity, and their mean and descriptive ratings.

Table 1. Level of Mindfulness of Senior High School Students

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Observation	3.72	High
Description	3.16	Moderate
Acting with Awareness	2.72	Moderate
Non-Judgment	3.46	High
Non-Reactivity	3.05	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.23	Moderate

The table shows that observation ranked as the highest among the five indicators of mindfulness, with a mean score of 3.72, which puts it in the "high" category. This suggests that senior high school students are constantly mindful of their experiences. The result shows that respondents' experiences demonstrate a high degree of mindfulness, especially in their inner and outer awareness. This explains how senior high school students are highly perceptive.

The findings support the hypothesis put forth by Desrosiers et al. (2014), who stated that observation has a big impact on students learning. This means that observation has a big impact on their strategies for learning the English language. By practicing observant awareness, students can create their learning strategies based on what they see in the environment and internal factors. The results of the current study support Desrosiers' claim, which highlights the role of observation in influencing students' learning processes. The student's capability to adjust their learning strategies can be attributed to their heightened level of mindfulness, particularly during observation.

Based on the result, the lowest indicator is "acting with awareness," which is under the "moderate" category and has a mean score of 2.72. This suggests that the Senior High School students are occasionally mindful of their experience. This study shows a remarkable amount of mindfulness among the students in their daily experiences, even though it scored lower than other markers. Even while their perceptions may not directly emphasize conscious action, their general attention is nevertheless apparent. This highlights a base of consciousness in their experiences, but one that might not be as involved as in other areas. As a result, even while "acting with awareness" may not be as well-known, it nevertheless adds to the student body's overall awareness.

As a result, mindfulness is associated with heightened attentive awareness (Moix et al., 2021). It appears from this research that even mild mindfulness, as the ones Senior High School students showed when it came to "acting with awareness," can nevertheless help to improve attentive awareness. Hence, even while this part of mindfulness might not get as much attention as it deserves, its existence nevertheless contributes significantly to the development of a more widespread mindfulness culture among students.

The cumulative mean of 3.23, as shown in Table 1, indicates that Senior High School students have achieved a moderate level of mindfulness. This suggests that although there may be times when students exhibit mindfulness in their experiences, there may also be other situations in which they need to be more focused or involved. It doesn't clearly point to a lack of mindfulness, nor does it strongly suggest one. Rather, it suggests a well-rounded viewpoint that acknowledges current mindfulness practices and leaves opportunities for growth.

This research provides strong support for the idea put forth by Bockmann and Yu (2022), who noted the viability, acceptance, and significant benefits of implementing mindfulness strategies in educational settings. Their claim emphasizes how mindfulness interventions can have a big impact on students' language learning strategies. Furthermore, this is in perfect harmony with the explanations provided by Winters (2022). According to him, these interventions can provide improvements in a number of areas, such as cognitive abilities, memory, and attention, which will provide a strong basis for better English language learning strategies and general well-being in the students. The results highlight the various advantages of incorporating mindfulness strategies into educational settings by bridging conflicting viewpoints, eventually leading to a more thorough and effective approach to promoting students' growth.

Level of Psychological Capital of Senior High School Students

Table 2 shows senior high school students' psychological capital. The indicator of psychological capital (optimism, resilience, self-efficacy, and hope) is presented together with its mean and descriptive scores.

Table 2. *Level of Psychological Capital of Senior High School Students*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Optimism	4.00	High
Resilience	3.66	High
Self-efficacy	3.32	Moderate
Hope	3.81	High
Overall Mean	3.70	High

Out of the four psychological capital indicators, respondents thought optimism had the highest mean score (4.00). Data-wise, optimism receives a mean score of 4.00 or above. This indicates that the remark regarding how they view themselves was acknowledged by Senior High School students. This suggests that a key component of students' psychological capital is their strong feelings of optimism. Respondents believe that others or themselves are very optimistic. This indicates that they probably have an optimistic view of life, remain upbeat, and generally anticipate success in their pursuits.

This result is consistent with the study of Genç and Arslan (2021), who found that optimism plays a major role in reducing the negative impacts of stress on people's well-being. The results of this study confirm that having an optimistic outlook is the best coping strategy. It can help students manage the challenges and pressures they face, which in turn increases their psychological resilience and improves their quality of life. This emphasizes how important optimism is for enhancing psychological capital in general, which in turn helps students maintain good mental health in a variety of situations.

The table shows that self-efficacy is the lowest indicator, with a mean score of 3.32, which means "moderate". This indicates that Senior High School students moderately acknowledged the statement about how they think about themselves. This suggests that students demonstrated a moderate degree of recognition with respect to statements evaluating their self-efficacy beliefs. The neutral position reveals neither they strongly confirmed nor denied their confidence in different areas of their talents.

The result highlights the significance of the discovery of Sabouripour et al. (2021), who said self-efficacy is the mediating factor in the relationship between students' psychological capital and resilience. In his statement, he emphasizes the importance of confidence in overcoming any hindrances and giving importance to their objectives. This is the way by which they practice their resilience levels to influence their psychological capital. As a result, it'll give attention to how different psychological capitals are interrelated to the possible benefits of interventions aimed at boosting self-efficacy.

As shown in Table 2, the overall mean score of Senior High School students' psychological capital is 3.70, which is considered "high." This indicates that Senior High School students acknowledged the statement about how they think about themselves. This means that respondents agreed to several points of view regarding the psychological capital indicators that were evaluated in the study. This further validates student's support for the existence of psychological traits, including hope, optimism, resilience, and self-efficacy in themselves or in their peers. It implies that the students have a foundation of psychological capital, which helps them deal with stress, overcome obstacles, and succeed in their academic and personal endeavors.

This corroborates the ideas of Martinez et al. (2019), Santisi et al. (2020), and Slåtten et al. (2021), who pointed out the huge importance of considering psychological capital practices in addition to the conventional predictors for academic accomplishment. They involved a thorough investigation and utilization of positive human characteristics and psychological capital that could be measured, developed, and skillfully controlled to improve teaching methods and raise student achievement in the classroom while supporting the general welfare of students and teachers. They clarified the critical importance of developing psychological capital and applying it wisely in educational settings to support students' resilience, self-determination, and, eventually, academic success.

Level of English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students

The extent to which Senior High School students employ various English language learning methodologies is demonstrated in Table 3. A detailed summary of the mean score and description for each component, which includes speaking, listening, reading, and writing, is provided.

Table 3. *Level of English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Speaking	3.81	High
Listening	3.32	Moderate
Reading	3.66	High
Writing	4.00	High
Overall Mean	3.70	High

A mean score of 4.00 across the four indicators in English language learning strategies indicates a high degree of agreement regarding the writing skills of the respondents. It appears from this that Senior High School students agreed with the assertion regarding their

proficiency in writing the language they are studying in class. Results show that students are proficient writers in English. These results highlight how good senior high school students are in writing practice, resulting in improved English language learning strategies. Overall, the mean score of 4.00 means that the respondents are very confident in their writing skills in the language.

This result supports the findings of Ten Peze et al.'s research from 2021, which pointed out the idea that a creative written work is a result of one's personal commitment and faith. This shows how self-belief and determination are crucial factors in students' creative writing and in overall academic success. This emphasizes how important it is for educational strategies to support students' writing skills to find tactics that could develop students' trust in their potential and achieve the commitment required for writing.

The table shows that listening had the lowest score in all of the indicators, as indicated by its mean rating of 3.32, or "moderate". This indicates that Senior High School students moderately acknowledged the statement about the language they learn at school. This means that students acknowledged their proficiency in language learning to a moderate extent. Although students did not strongly agree or disagree with the statement on their listening skills, they did acknowledge its usefulness in the language they are taught in school. It highlights how important it is to include listening strategies in the language learning curriculum and put them in place to help students enhance their listening skills.

This result supports the findings of Demir and Tavil (2021), who pointed out the efficiency of textbook and technology-based resources in promoting the enhanced listening abilities of students. By implementing a variety of teaching strategies and resources, students' listening abilities surely improve. It suggests that using technology-based tools with traditional textbook materials is a big contribution to a diverse approach to improving students' listening abilities. This gives importance to how impactful it is to have a variety of learning strategies in language learning courses in order not just to maximize English language learning strategies but also to accommodate the different learning styles of the students.

As shown in Table 3, Senior High School students' overall mean score is 3.70, which falls into the "high" category. This indicates that senior high school students acknowledged the statement about the language they learned at school. This means that they agree with the opinion stated about their English language learning strategies. This agreement means that the instructional strategies used by senior high schools are effective in improving students' English language learning. The average mean of 3.70 indicates that the students are very satisfied with their experience using their language learning strategies.

This result validates the idea presented by Jelínková (2022), who stated that English language learning is a result of student's motivation. Furthermore, Putri et al. (2022) added the importance of parents to their student's academic achievement as well as the importance of community and school-related elements. These highlight the diverse strategies of education for a comprehensive approach that takes into account the impact of students' language learning processes.

Test of Relationship between Mindfulness and English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students

Table 4 shows the test of the relationship between senior high school students' mindfulness and their strategies for learning the English language.

Table 4. *Test of Relationship between Mindfulness and English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students*

<i>Variable paired with Students' English Language Learning Strategies</i>	<i>Pearson's R-value</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Students' Mindfulness	0.594	0.000	Significant

The Pearson correlation coefficient (R-value) of 0.594 and the significant p-value of 0.000 shows that students' mindfulness and their English language learning strategies have a strong positive correlation. This result implies that when students' mindfulness levels increase, their English language learning strategies become more effective as well. Based on this positive correlation, it can be inferred that students with high levels of mindfulness may also show improvement in focus, concentration, and cognition—all of which are beneficial for senior high school students' English language learning.

The result agreed with the statement of Lin (2020), who said that mindfulness and English language learning strategies go together hand-in-hand for the student to have successful language learning.

The result shows agreement with Lin's claim, which is that the level of mindfulness awareness hones the inner and outer environment among senior high school students. Having a mindfulness strategy can help students become more successful at using practical strategies, especially when studying English. Integrating mindfulness practices into the context of language learning significantly contributes to the growing body of research. It stresses how important it is to recognize mindfulness as a useful tool for enhancing students' strategies for learning English and their general academic performance.

Test of Relationship between Psychological Capital and English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students

Table 5 shows the test of the relationship between senior high school students' psychological capital and their strategies for learning the English language.

Table 5. *Test of Relationship between Psychological Capital and English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students*

<i>Variable paired with Students' English Language Learning Strategies</i>	<i>Pearson's R-value</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Students' Psychological Capital	0.631	0.000	Significant

The Pearson correlation coefficient (R-value) of 0.631 and the significant p-value of 0.000 show that students' psychological capital and their English language learning strategies have a strong positive correlation. This research implies that when students' psychological capital increases, their performance, and English language learning strategies get better as well. The substantial positive correlation means that students who possess higher levels of psychological capital are more likely to demonstrate higher levels of motivation, confidence, and perseverance when learning the English language. This highlights the important role of psychological capital in the student's academic development and, overall, their success in the English language.

Sánchez-Cardona et al. (2021) highlighted the need to allocate resources toward building psychological capital for students. With the use of psychological resources and English language learning strategies, educational institutions can successfully improve student satisfaction. This view highlights how educational environments can be made more fulfilling by placing a higher priority on students' psychological capital. Exercising psychological capital can be successfully facilitated with the use of English language learning strategies, Lin (2020).

Indicators of Mindfulness that Significantly Influence the English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students

Table 6 presents the Indicators of Mindfulness that Significantly Influence the English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students.

Table 6. *Indicators of Mindfulness that Significantly Influence the English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students*

English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students							
Students' Mindfulness	Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients			Interpretations
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on Ho	
Constant	1.417	0.227		6.232	0.000	Reject	Significant
Observation	0.319	0.055	0.425	5.826	0.000	Reject	Significant
Description	0.134	0.055	0.175	2.424	0.017	Reject	Significant
Acting with Awareness	0.038	0.048	0.056	0.787	0.432	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Non-judgment	0.062	0.054	0.086	1.153	0.251	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Non-Reactivity	0.112	0.067	0.123	1.674	0.096	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
R = 0.651		R ² = 0.424	F-value = 22.6397		p-value = 0.000		

The table shows the regression analysis results providing insightful information about mindfulness that significantly influences the English language learning strategies of senior high school students, especially in relation to the following indicators: observation, description, acting with awareness, non-judgment, and non-reactivity.

Based on the result, observation and description have significant unstandardized coefficients, which means that these indicators of mindfulness have a significant impact on senior high school students' English language learning strategies. A student who is focused and certain of their emotions may result in successful language learning. In that regard, students should pay more attention to developing their observational skills to be able to enhance their English language learning strategies, Pratiwi and Ayu (2020).

On the other hand, acting with awareness, non-judgment, and non-reactivity do not show any statistical significance. This indicates that these indicators of mindfulness have little effect on the English language learning strategies used by Senior High School students. The overall model explains that the combined effect of the variables included in the model can explain around 42.4% of the variance in English language learning strategies with an R-squared value of 0.424 and an R-value of 0.651. The whole model's statistical significance is further supported by the F-value of 22.6397 and p-value of 0.000, which substantiates the significance between mindfulness and English language learning strategies of senior high school students.

Overall, the regression analysis emphasizes mindfulness indicators, namely, description and observation, which are important in predicting senior high school students' English language learning strategies. Harmenita and Tiarina (2013) stated that these strategies are expected to increase students' motivation and ability to learn. It also suggests that there are other factors that may influence senior high school students' strategies to learn the English language. More research could be done to check on these variables.

Indicators of Psychological Capital that Significantly Influence the English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students

The table presents psychological capital indicators that have a significant influence on the English language learning strategies of senior high school students.

Table 7. *Indicators of Psychological Capital that Significantly Influence the English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students*

English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students								
Students' Psychological Capital	Psychological	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Decision on Ho	Interpretation
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.		
Constant		1.318	0.219		6.021	0.000	Reject	Significant
Hope		0.228	0.063	0.302	3.610	0.000	Reject	Significant
Self-Efficacy		-0.021	0.072	-0.024	-0.285	0.776	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Resilience		0.448	0.084	0.487	5.322	0.000	Reject	Significant
Optimism		-0.017	0.069	-0.022	-0.248	0.805	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

R = 0.676 R² = 0.456 F-value = 32.524 p-value = 0.000

The table shows the regression analysis results, which provide insightful information about psychological capital that significantly influences the English language learning strategies of senior high school students, especially in relation to the following indicators: optimism, resilience, self-efficacy, and hope.

Based on the result, Hope and Resilience indicate that these measures of psychological capital and Senior High School students' strategies for learning English have significant nonstandard coefficients. This supports the idea of Genç and Arslan (2021), who stated that hope is a useful resource for one's subjective well-being. Chen and Padilla (2019) also pointed out that the development of resilience is a result of being positive. These emotional experiences support students' ability to see learning settings imaginatively. This implies that students who are more resilient and hopeful demonstrate superior English language learning strategies.

However, in this study, the coefficient for Self-Efficacy does not attain statistical significance, suggesting that this aspect of psychological capital does not exert a notable influence on English language learning strategies among Senior High School students. Similarly, the coefficient for optimism is also not statistically significant. There are likely other factors contributing to students' English language learning strategies.

The overall model, characterized by an R-value of 0.676 and an R-squared value of 0.456, elucidates that approximately 45.6% of the variability in English language learning strategies can be elucidated by the collective impacts of the variables incorporated in the model. This suggests that while hope and resilience (Lei and Lei, 2023) play significant roles in Students' English language learning strategies, other factors likely contribute to these variables. The F-value of 32.524, accompanied by a p-value of 0.000, signifies that the overall model is statistically significant.

Predicting English language learning strategies is crucial among senior high school students, Lei and Lei (2023). The regression analysis results highlight the importance of hope and resilience. It suggests that students' strategies for learning English may be influenced by other factors that are not included in the study, which needs to be further investigated. More research could investigate other variables.

Regression Analysis on Combined Significant Influence of Mindfulness and Psychological Capital to the English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students

Table 8 shows the regression analysis on the combined significant influence of mindfulness and psychological capital on senior high school students' English language learning strategies.

The result shows substantial unstandardized coefficients on students' mindfulness and psychological capital, suggesting that these variables have a major influence on how they learn the English language. This means that a student who typically has higher levels of mindfulness shows stronger English language learning strategies (Vorontsova-Wenger, 2020) and has a more resilient psychological capital (Sánchez-Cardona et al., 2021).

Table 8. *Regression Analysis on Combined Significant Influence of Mindfulness and Psychological Capital to the English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students*

English Language Learning Strategies of Senior High School Students							
Combined Results	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Decision on Ho	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.		
Constant	0.685	0.235		2.912	0.004	Reject	Significant
Students' Mindfulness	0.427	0.069	0.387	6.218	0.000	Reject	Significant
Students' Psychological Capital	0.440	0.060	0.455	7.310	0.000	Reject	Significant
R = 0.719		R ² = 0.517		F-value = 84.006		p-value = 0.000	

The association between psychological capital and mindfulness in senior high school students' English language learning strategies is also strongly supported by the F-value of 84.006, which is accompanied by a p-value of 0.000, indicating that the total model is statistically significant. Overall, the model shows that psychological capital and mindfulness together may explain around 51.7% of the variance in English language learning strategies (R-squared = 0.517, R-value = 0.719). This implies that these factors have a huge influence on senior high school students' ability to forecast English language learning strategies, Gordani and Sadeghzadeh (2023).

In summary, the regression analysis emphasizes the important roles that psychological capital and mindfulness have in influencing senior high school students' English language learning strategies. These results underline the necessity for educators and legislators to take into account treatments and tactics that cultivate psychological capital and mindfulness in order to improve the efficacy of language learning in educational settings. Moreover, the noteworthy influence of mindfulness and psychological capital implies that a comprehensive strategy for language learning that tackles socio-emotional aspects in addition to academic proficiencies could result in enhanced English language learning strategies and enhanced student achievement.

Conclusions

The study leads to a conclusion that psychological capital and mindfulness have a substantial influence on 51.7% of English language learning strategies of senior high school students. Thus, social cognitive self-regulation theory on self-regulation is confirmed by continuous self-influence exercises through a primary self-regulatory mechanism that has three main sub-functions that govern human behavior. These comprise judgment, affective self-reaction, and self-monitoring.

In light of the findings, it is advised that language learning programs include self-regulation training, psychological capital development, and mindfulness activities. These techniques can improve learners' self-awareness, self-monitoring, and self-belief. Learners should be given regular feedback and assistance in applying these strategies, and peer collaboration and mentorship should be encouraged to create a friendly environment. It is imperative that these strategies be continuously evaluated and adjusted in response to feedback and new research. Additionally, by examining novel factors or alternative locations, future studies should examine the validity of the idea.

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